

**TEACHING METHODOLOGY AND TECHNOLOGY IN FOREIGN
LANGUAGE LESSONS****Kharatova Shakhlo Khakimovna**

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Annotation: This paper covers the procedure, methods and techniques of teaching foreign language lessons. According to the new national education, in order to achieve its goals, it is necessary to improve the forms of organization of the educational process, to introduce new technologies and methods of teaching, to increase student's interest in learning. The formation of universal learning activities is fundamental task of education.

Key words: educational system, translation method, right method, mixed method, comparative method, training, collective activity, inductive and deductive.

Active methods of education not only help students to actively think and engage in practical activities during the learning process, but also positive teaching helps to form motivation, reveal and develop creative abilities, helps to master the learning material with high efficiency. . Taking into account that foreign language classes are not our mother tongue, it is a difficult task to teach this subject to students, so it is necessary to conduct the classes with quality skills. In the course of the lesson, teachers should use methods that are effective for students at each stage of the lesson. Nowadays, new methods and methods of teaching subjects are being developed and they are being tested in practice. At first, teaching a foreign language was considered to be the study of this language system, but in the following years, the purpose of teaching was to develop students' foreign language speech. New requirements for the results of educational activities serve to develop the basic form of the educational process.

In the foreign language teaching methodology, the term "Method" has three meanings. The first is all general trends in the history of methodology (translation method, correct method, comparative method, mixed method), the second is the teaching system, and the third is the method of activity in the lesson.

The following methods are widely used in teaching foreign language classes:

- Translation method - you can find out what kind of method it is, in which information in a foreign language is translated into the native language. Among the translation methods, the most common ones are known as "Grammar-translation method" and "Text translation method". Both translation methods are used only for educational purposes. A foreign language is learned in a receptive way.

- The main reason for the origin of the name of the correct method is that during teaching in the correct method, there is a direct association between the foreign language word and the subject, that is, a mental connection, bypassing the mother tongue. A connection attempt was made. This method is used to teach foreign language grammar. Two of the modern forms of the correct method - audiolingual and audiovisual methods - are widespread.
- Mixed method - this method has absorbed the scientific and practical aspects of two methodological directions. A different form of the mixed method was created by mixing the principles of the correct and comparative methods.
- Comparative method - the full name of this method is called "Conscious comparative method". In the first form of the conscious-comparative method, the rule is basically an exercise. Practical rules are summarized during the exercise in a modern way. The student is not specially engaged in comparing, memorizing and telling the rules, and gathering theoretical knowledge.

Another type of expression of the term method is the methods used practically in the process of teaching a foreign language:

- ❖ dating,
- ❖ exercise,
- ❖ application.

In the methodology of teaching a foreign language: there is also a method of receiving training, which is a long-term relationship between the teacher and students aimed at transferring and mastering certain knowledge, skills and abilities. Collective activity is the distribution of collective work among members aimed at achieving a common result at the same time. Such methods also serve to increase the efficiency of science teaching. At the same time, in the process of applying these methods, one should not forget to organize cognitive activities, such as working on the blackboard, filling in tables, writing reports, and working with textbooks.

According to the traditions established in local pedagogy, teaching methods are divided into three groups:

- Verbal, visual, practical.
- Reproductive, explanatory, illustrative, searching, research and problem discussion.
- Inductive and deductive materials.

It is precisely the role of innovative technologies in the process of effective and high-quality foreign language lessons. Forming lessons in the context of

information technologies is a powerful factor that enriches the child's intellectual, moral, and aesthetic development and therefore introduces him to the world of information culture. The formation of ICT competences of students occurs within the framework of the system-activity approach. The goal is to form and further develop the universal character of students.

The basis of foreign language lessons covers four areas - listening, speaking, reading and writing.

1) In the course of the lesson, it is not necessary to develop only speaking skills, and therefore, teaching listening is one of the practical tasks of teaching a foreign language.

2) When teaching reading, information can be obtained from texts, new words are learned, and it is necessary to teach using different techniques, such as sight-seeing. There are similar types or readability in foreign methodology (skimming, scanning).

3) Speaking plays a key role in teaching oral speech of a foreign language. Exercises and assignments must be completed to form it.

4) Teaching writing is also important. For example, writing a letter helps to analyze and synthesize individual information. Even today, writing skills in Czech are in high demand.

The lesson is the main form of organizing educational activities. Therefore, pedagogical skills are also required from teachers in the course of lessons.

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